

RDM Requirements

Overview of funders' data policies

Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)

"In the interest of transparency and to enable research to be referred to and reused by others, whenever possible researchers make the research data and principal materials on which a publication is based available in recognised archives and repositories in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).¹

Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice (2019); especially relevant:

- Guideline 7: cross-phase quality assurance
- Guideline 10: legal and ethical frameworks, usage rights
- Guideline 11: methods and standards
- Guideline 12: documentation
- Guideline 13: providing public access to research results
- Guideline 17: archiving
- data handling in compliance with the FAIR Principles²

A funding proposal should include:

- ✓ how research data are collected, generated or evaluated during the course of the project
- ✓ discipline-specific procedures for quality management, handling and long-term archiving of research data
- ✓ data types and discipline-specific standards
- ✓ information on the choice of a suitable repository, if data sharing is intended
- ✓ any rights of third parties affected
- ✓ data publishing strategy

European Commission (Horizon 2020)

The Commission is running a flexible pilot under Horizon2020 called the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDpilot). The ORD pilot aims to improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by Horizon2020 projects and takes into account the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialisation and Intellectual Property Rights(IPR), privacy concerns, security as well as data management and preservation questions.³

Since 01.01.2017 Open Data is the default (non-compulsory for ERC Grants)

- ✓ handling data according to the principle: "As open as possible, as closed as necessary"
- ✓ make data available in an open access repository at the latest after the end of the project
- ✓ primarily applicable to research data that form the basis of a publication (voluntary for other data)
- ✓ data handling in compliance with the FAIR Principles²
- ✓ "opt-out" possible at any time, but must be justified (possible reasons: intellectual property rights, data protection, threat to the project objective)

Further regulations:

- Data Management Plan (DMP) is a deliverable in month 6; update required in case of major changes in the RDM concept or the composition of the project consortium

¹ https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/rechtliche_rahmenbedingungen/gute_wissenschaftliche_praxis/kodex_gwp_en.pdf

² <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

³ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

RDM Requirements

Overview of funders' data policies

Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF)

"Irrespective of the economic prospects for success, the scientific and/or technical prospects for success should be presented (with a time horizon), among other things, how the planned results can be used in other ways (e.g. in the public sector, databases, networks, transfer offices, etc.). This should also include possible cooperations with other institutions, companies, networks, research centres, etc. (translated from German)."⁵

A concept for handling research data (usage plan) is required. It should include information on:

- ✓ data types
- ✓ discipline-specific standards
- ✓ the repository of choice or any other form of data preservation
- ✓ archiving the research data for at least 10 years (where/how?)
- ✓ cost of data preparation

Educational research: a special case

„After completion of the project, the applicants undertake to make the data obtained through the project available in a transferable form at an appropriate facility (e.g. GESIS – Leibniz Institute for Social Sciences or a research data centre) with the aim of enabling long-term data backup, secondary evaluation or re-use. There, the data is archived, documented and made available on request of the scientific community“⁶

- open data mandate
- data management plan (DMP) mandatory⁷

This handout provides an overview of the requirements of the three largest research funding organisations. If you have any questions about other funders and their funding guidelines, we will gladly advise you personally. Contact us at <https://forschungsdaten-thueringen.de/kontakt.html>

⁵ BMBF: Richtlinien für Zuwendungsanträge auf Ausgabenbasis -AZA.2013 (http://foerderportal.bund.de/easy/easy_index.php?auswahl=easy_formulare&formularschrank=bmbf#t1)

⁶ <https://www.bmbf.de/foerderung/bekanntmachung.php?B=774>

⁷ http://wiki.bildungsserver.de/bilder/upload/checkliste_datenmanagement.pdf